

Assistive Technologies for Physically Challenged Students in Kerala: a study on user's awareness and perception

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to investigate the physically challenged student's awareness and use of assistive technologies in the schools of Kerala. The survey questionnaire tool was used to collect data from 111 physically challenged students, who are studying in 45 schools in Thiruvananthapuram, Ernakulam and Kozhikode districts. The analysis revealed that 55 (49.5%) students are aware of assistive technologies. Girls are more aware and updated (50.5%) than the boys (49.5%). All the physically challenged students who participated in the study opined that they didn't get any instruction on using the library services and e-resources. It was found that school authorities (87.4%) are the major sources for giving training to physically challenged. It was also noted that no student is confident enough about the ability to use assistive technologies and devices and 24.3 per cent students considered their ability to use assistive technologies are average. Among the students, 66 (59.5%) have an e-mail account and almost all the students responded positively on the availability of computer education in their schools and the response rate is 96.4 per cent.

Keywords: Assistive technologies, Awareness, Perception, Differently-abled, Students, Kerala

INTRODUCTION

Disability is a major concern of the society. The governmental and non- governmental sectors have been making efforts to fight it but it still remains a big challenge. Many initiatives were undertaken to improve the empowerment of differently-abled in developing countries especially in India. While considering the educational aspects of differently-abled in the state, most of the special schools are devoted mainly for visually challenged, hearing impaired and mentally

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challenged students. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) rehabilitation guidelines, disability is impairment of an individual as it affects his or her role in life, such as an inability to work because of a health condition. Any impairment which limits the physical function of limbs, fine bones, or gross motor ability is physical disability/physical impairment.

Libraries have always had problems in providing information for differently-abled people in their preferred format. Libraries have a moral obligation to provide services to all its users equally. To meet the information needs of differently-abled students, libraries need to be adapted with proper assistive equipments and basic infrastructural facilities. They have the same library and information needs as everyone else, although they may require adaptations in the form of service. Libraries are meant to help users to take maximum advantage of library resources to meet their information needs.

Technology can change lives and make social impact. Though there have progress in the educational aspects for the differently-abled people, it hasn't seen assistive technology play a role in their progress. Assistive technologies can help in ensuring the medium of instruction, and can be sufficiently modified to help differently-abled to overcome the challenges. If these technologies are implemented in libraries the library can be made inclusive. Proper awareness about assistive technologies are required to differently-abled. They should be properly informed about the wide range of assistive technologies that can help them access the required information easily. Assistive technologies are intended to maximize a person's abilities while minimizing the challenges of having a disability. Every library should include at least a single assistive technology or adaptive devices for each category of differently-abled, which helps to transform a traditional library into a learning resource centre.

The study was conducted by selecting sample from three regions of Kerala state, which include Kozhikode from the northern region (Malabar), Ernakulam from the middle part (Kochi) and Thiruvananthapuram from the southern region (Travancore), so that a state wise perception can be elicited.

Assistive Technologies

Assistive technologies are devices or products that are designed to enhance the functional capabilities of persons with disabilities. Typically, devices are prescribed to meet specific activity goals of clients and to achieve a goodness of fit between the person, their desired activity and the environments in which they are living. Many assistive devices are designed to reduce the limitations resulting from impairments and illness, and provide alternative or adaptive ways to do specific activities. Wheelchairs enable persons with a mobility impairment to move around

their home and community, a bath bench allows a person to transfer into a tub sitting rather than standing, and electronic writing aids provide users with an alternative way to produce written work. ATDs are prescribed to improve participation in home and community activities, and by doing so are expected to enhance quality of life.

The success and applicability of an AT device is measured by its actual usage, ease in accessibility by its users and in their satisfaction in interaction with their environment. It is essential to ensure that the assistive devices are need-based, inexpensive to produce, purchase and maintain, easy to use, and effective, which can be ensured by the direct involvement of the potential users at each stage of designing and development.

There is a wide range of assistive technology available to compensate users who have motor disabilities. For persons with physical impairments, to access library resources in digital format, the computer keyboard and mouse can present a significant barrier. Several common input modifications include adapted keyboards, on-screen keyboards, alternative communication programs, and voice recognition. Other devices commonly used are: Sticky Keys, On-screen keyboards, Voice recognition and dictation systems, Head Mouse, Foot Pedal Mouse, Head stick Mouse (Venkatesha *et al.*, 2016).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Several studies have been conducted to study the awareness and use of assistive technologies by the differently-abled students. But very few studies have been conducted in the physically challenged student's use of assistive technologies.

Haque *et al.* (2020) discussed the information need, seeking behaviour, and habits of the library use by the physically challenged students of Rajshahi in Bangladesh. The results showed that textbooks, newspaper are the most popular types of sources of information which are used for mainly preparing for the examination. Facebook, YouTube were significant sources of information as sources of entertainment.

Ahammed (2018) conducted a study to determine education professionals' opinions regarding the use of assistive technology in the classroom. Twenty-eight students and staff members from a Midwestern University in the United States participated in the study; generally, participants were asked if they support the use of assistive technology or not, and to pinpoint obstacles that might prevent people from using assistive technology. Sudhier and Soman (2018) investigated the use of library resources and services provided for the physically challenged students in Kerala. The study revealed that physical access of the library building is a major problem faced by them. The use of materials shows that, most of them are depending on printed materials.

Venkatesha *et al.* (2016) carried out a study to highlight to what extent the physically challenged library users are familiar with the technology used for accessing and reading. The extent of orientation and training required for making use of these tools or equipment effectively is also analysed and the study suggested various types of assistive technologies available for physically challenged students which can be used to access, read and record information. Tella *et al.* (2015) carried out a study to find out the physically challenged undergraduates satisfaction with library and information services in Kwara state higher education institutions. The study recommended training of library staff to meet the needs of physically challenged users and inclusion of these special group of users in the decision making process of the library concerning their collection development.

Sanman and Kumar (2015) examined the user's awareness and satisfaction level with the available AT facilities for the people with disabilities in National Capital Region libraries of India. A total of 375 users in all the 15 libraries were selected randomly and the users 'Strongly agree' towards the need of the ATs to work in the digital environment. This study is first to explore the viewpoint of people with disabilities regarding the ATs available in NCR libraries of India. Lidstrom and Hemmingsson (2014) conducted a study to investigate types of ICT items and how ICT is being used by students with physical disabilities, and described the benefits of ICT use in school activities. Revealed that type of ICT used differed among impairment groups, and ICT seemed to be especially beneficial for writing, spelling, and communication. Bhattacharya, Ramachandran, Selvanayagi (2014) discussed in detail about the library services for the physically challenged students. Authors pointed that the primary purpose of a library is to provide its users with increased access to knowledge. The article deals with the basic components for physically challenged in libraries like parking and accessible pathway, internal circulation and entrance of the library.

Upadhyay and Sharma (2013) carried out a study to examine the feasibility of using assistive computing technologies (ACT) in India and explored the factors affecting its adoption. The study revealed that adoption of ACT by rural population is low compared to urban. It was also highlighted by the respondents during the study that very few doctors and physiotherapists treating physically disabled were aware of ACT. Solarin (2013) analysed the roles of government and academic libraries in ensuring that library materials and information services are accessible to the physically challenged users. Ilayaraja and Manoharan (2012) carried out a study to find out the library and information services to the physically challenged students for mobility in the university libraries in Tiruchirappalli district, Tamil Nadu. Solarin (2012) conducted a study to examine information availability and services provided for the physically challenged students and to examine accessibility of the physically challenged students to the library and library resources

and also to identify problems confronting the physically challenged students in the academic libraries in Ogun state. Cummings (2011) presented a table that provides librarians, teachers, and parents with helpful information on assistive / adaptive technology resources for students with disabilities. Colean (2011) discussed some of the major issues that impede successful implementation of assistive technology for students with physical disabilities and also provides a checklist that teachers and related services personnel can use when considering assistive technology for curriculum access. Ari and Fethi (2010) examined the assistive technology needs of university students with disabilities and the availability of these technologies. Data collected through questionnaire method revealed that students with disabilities utilized assistive technology for different purposes, such as writing and conducting research, when the resources and support were available.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study are:

- To find out the physically challenged student's awareness of library services
- To study the student's awareness of assistive technologies
- To analyse the methods of learning assistive technologies
- To explore the opinion on the use of assistive technologies
- To study the awareness and use of computer-aided services
- To study the use of e-resources
- To identify the assistive technologies available to reduce the barriers to access of information.

METHODOLOGY

A survey-based method using questionnaires is used to explore the information needs of the physically challenged students. The study used stratified random sampling method, for the collection of sample population. Sample was selected from three regions of Kerala state, which include Kozhikode from the northern (Malabar) region, Ernakulam from the middle (Kochi) and Thiruvananthapuram from the south (Travancore). 45 schools (15 schools from each district) were covered for collecting the data. Students studying in special schools (government and aided special schools) and those studying in regular schools under Inclusive Education for Disabled at Secondary Stage (IEDSS) from three districts were taken for the study. The collected data was further analysed using SPSS software, which was used for specific, descriptive and inferential statistics. Appropriate tests like Chi –Square, was used to establish statistically significant analysis and verify generally held beliefs.

Census data 2011 revealed that there are a total of 7,61,843 differently-abled persons in the state, which include physically challenged students 17640(21%) in Kozhicode district, 15186(23%) in Ernakulam district and 19095(24%) in Thiruvananthapuram district.

SCOPE AND RELEVANCE

The study would be helpful in getting a fairly good idea on the use of assistive technologies of physically challenged students in the state and their information requirements. The study would be found useful to those who propose to launch special libraries and LRCs, as well as to those who are already in the area. The information needs of students with special needs should be met with adequate facilities in the new digital era. If an information system is implemented to meet the information needs of differently-abled students, it will be a boon for them. This study is particularly significant since such a comprehensive study incorporating all aspects of the information needs of physically challenged students in Kerala has never been conducted so far. Therefore, the outcome of the study would, it is hoped, provide valuable information to the academicians, librarians, sociologists, policy planners and the government.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Information of the Respondents

The Table 1 outlines the background information of the students covered under the study. It includes district, gender, age etc. and are categorized on the basis of their types of disability.

Table 1 reveals that among the 1213 respondents, 717 (59%) are boys and 496 (41%) are female students. While considering the age group of the students, majority of them belong to the age group of 13-15 (782), those who are studying in high school section and 431 students are from

Table 1: Demographic Information

Demographic Information		Physically Challenged	
		Count	Percentage
District	TVPM	45	40.5
	EKLM	28	25.2
	KKD	38	34.2
Gender	Male	55	49.5
	Female	56	50.5
Age	13-15	66	59.5
	16-18	45	40.5

higher secondary section, which belongs of the age group 16-18. The analysis demonstrates that among the 3 districts taken for the study, Kozhikode is having the largest number of respondents, 675 students of which 185 students are visually challenged (27%), 452 hearing impaired (67%) and 38 (6%) physically challenged students.

Awareness of Library Provisions

To investigate the awareness level about the library facilities, an attempt has been made to collect information from the physically challenged students and the data collected is analyzed and presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Awareness of Library Provisions

It is evident from the figure that, 105 (94.6%) physically challenged students are aware of the library facilities in their school. Accessibility to the library is a major problem faced by physically challenged students. 54 (48.6%) students opined that the school library location is easily accessible. To provide proper library service to the students, assistance by a staff is essential. But as teachers are having the charge of school libraries, only 2.7 per cent students responded positively about the assistance they are getting from library staff. The physically challenged students opined that there is no provision of library period in their school time table,

Services for Physically Challenged Students

Table 2 shows the physically challenged students' response on the library services.

Table 2: Library Services for Physically Challenged

Library services		Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)	χ^2	p
Book shelves in the library can be easily accessible	Yes	2(3.6%)	13(23.2%)	15(13.5%)	9.1**	0.003
	No	53(96.4%)	43(76.8%)	96(86.5%)		
Infrastructure facilities are helpful for free moving of all categories of students	Yes	5(9.1%)	12(21.4%)	17(15.3%)	3.26	0.071
	No	50(90.9%)	44(78.6%)	94(84.7%)		
Library is providing information in your preferred format	Yes	47(85.5%)	53(94.6%)	100(90.1%)	2.62	0.105
	No	8(14.5%)	3(5.4%)	11(9.9%)		
School library helpful in meeting your academic needs	Yes	26(47.3%)	31(55.4%)	57(51.4%)	0.73	0.394
	No	29(52.7%)	25(44.6%)	54(48.6%)		
How many times you have been given library instruction on how to use e resources and library resources	Once	0	0	0	-	-
	Never	55(100%)	56(100%)	111(100%)		
Do you like to visit your school library	Yes	44(80.0%)	51(91.1%)	95(85.6%)	2.76	0.097
	No	11(20.0%)	5(8.9%)	16(14.4%)		
Institution provides training for daily life skill activities	Yes	44(80.0%)	50(89.3%)	94(84.7%)	1.84	0.174
	No	11(20.0%)	6(10.7%)	17(15.3%)		

All the students who participated in the study opined that they didn't get any instruction on using the library services and e-resources. 90.1 per cent students are getting information in the preferred formats from the library, whereas 86.5 per cent says that they can't access the library shelves easily.

It is evident that 85.6% students like to visit their school library, while 84.7 per cent says that the infrastructural facilities in the library is not barrier free, and 57 (51.4%) students found school library helpful in meeting their academic needs. While 94 students responded that they are getting training for daily life skill activities from the institution. From the analysis shown in Table 4, it can be observed that there exists significant difference in the gender and the barriers in accessing book shelves. It is statistically proved through Chi-square tests that the barriers in accessing bookshelves among male students is significantly higher than that of female students.

Awareness of Assistive Technologies

Various types of assistive devices are available nowadays which helps differently-abled students to work independently in the modern digital world. The use of assistive technologies depends mainly on the awareness and knowledge of users. The awareness level of students are analyzed and is presented in the Table 3.

Table 3: Awareness of Assistive Technologies- Physically Challenged

		Aware		Not Aware		χ^2	p
		Count	Percent	Count	Percent		
Age	13 - 15	32	48.5	34	51.5	0.07	0.786
	16 - 18	23	51.1	22	48.9		
Gender	Male	28	50.9	27	49.1	0.08	0.776
	Female	27	48.2	29	51.8		
District	TVPM	21	46.7	24	53.3	5.11	0.078
	EKLM	10	35.7	18	64.3		
	KKD	24	63.2	14	36.8		

It is clear from the study that among the 111 physically challenged students, 55 (49.5%) students are aware of assistive technologies, which show a negative attitude towards new advancements and technologies by the physically challenged students. The response rate of students in the age group of 16-18 (51.1%) shows that their awareness level is higher than the students in the age of 13-15 (48.5%). Males (50.9%) are more updated and aware of technological advancements than females (48.2%). Physically challenged students from Kozhikode district (63.2%) shows higher response rate than the other two districts. While applying Chi-square test, it is seen that the awareness level of assistive technologies are independent of the age, gender and districts of the physically challenged students.

Method of Learning Assistive Technologies

Differently-abled students require special training in using internet and assistive technologies. The students were asked to indicate the methods of learning assistive technologies and the responses are presented in the Figure 2.

From the responses indicated in the Figure 2, it is clear that school authorities (87.4%) are the major sources for giving training to physically challenged. Analysis shows that students who got training from short term courses (27.9%) and assistance from family members (23.4%) are higher than self learned students (15.3%).

Figure 2: Method of Learning Assistive Technologies

Figure 3: Preference of Adaptive Devices

Preference of Adaptive Devices

The analysis on the preference of adaptive devices are shown in the Figure 3.

The study shows that students mostly use keyboard adaptations (40.5%) as assistive technology. 27 per cent students prefer to use screen keyboards and 15.3 per cent use head mouse and other devices. Only 5 students prefer to use voice recognition and dictation systems as assistive devices.

Opinion on the Use of Assistive Technologies

The students were asked to express their opinion and rate themselves about the ability to use assistive technologies. Results presented in Figure 4 reveals that no student is confident enough about the ability to use assistive technologies and devices. 24.3 per cent students considered their ability to use assistive technologies are average and 54.1 per cent students rated their ability in using assistive devices are bad.

Figure 4: Opinion on the Use of Assistive Technologies

Opinion on the Awareness and Use of Computer-aided Services

Data depicted in Table 4 presents details of the computer and internet facility in the library, whether the institution provides computer education for their students, whether they are getting assistance for using computers. The study also analyzes the usage of internet for checking e-mail, whether students owns e-mail accounts etc. Student's opinion about role of assistive technology to meet their goals are also analyzed and is presented here.

Among the students, 66(59.5%) students have an email account. To make the students aware of computer and internet resources, proper training should be provided. The study found that

Table 4: Awareness and Use of Computer-aided Services

Awareness and use of Computer-aided Services		PC	
		Count	Percentage
Do you have e-mail Id	Yes	66	59.5
	No	45	40.5
Institution provides computer education	Yes	107	96.4
	No	4	3.6
Computer and internet facility in your library	Yes	0	0.0
	No	111	100
Getting any assistance in using computers	Yes	21	18.9
	No	90	81.1
Using Assistive Technology will be a tool to achieve your goals	Agree	24	21.6
	Strongly Agree	66	59.5
	Partially Agree	21	18.9

most of the institutions are providing computer education to their students as part of the curriculum. Almost all the students responded positively to the availability of computer education in their schools and the response rate is 96.4%.

Even though every school provides computer education, the responses of students shows that they are not enjoying the benefits of computer and internet facility in their library services. All the physically challenged students responded negatively on the availability of computers in the library. Students’ needs proper training and assistance to make use of the computers, and the analysis reveals that they are getting assistance to an extent, mainly for computer usage for their educational purposes. The students were asked to respond whether the use of assistive technologies helps to achieve their goals, and the responses shows that 59.5 per cent of them strongly agrees that using assistive technology helps them to achieve their goals.

MAJOR FINDINGS

- Analysis revealed that majority of 49.5 per cent students are aware of assistive technologies.
- It is found that girls are more aware and updated than the boys.
- All the physically challenged students who participated in the study opined that they didn’t get any instruction on using the library services and e-resources.
- It was found that school authorities are the major sources for giving training to physically challenged.

- It was also noted that no student is confident enough about the ability to use assistive technologies and devices and 24.3 per cent students considered their ability to use assistive technologies are average.
- Among the students, 59.5 per cent have an email account and almost all the students responded positively on the availability of computer education in their schools.

CONCLUSION

It is found from the study that physically challenged students are not satisfied with the present library facilities and collection. All the students expressed their opinion of improving library facilities like seating facility, computer and internet facility in libraries, library collection, CDs, adding assistive devices and maintaining the physical access to the library. The study would be helpful in getting a fairly good idea of the present status of special libraries and library services for the challenged students in the state and their information requirements. The study would be found useful to those who propose to launch special libraries and LRCs, as well as to those who are already in the area. While studies have demonstrated the value and advances of assistive technology in educational scenario worldwide, the implementation of these tools in the classrooms and in libraries in Kerala has been seen as very slow. Most higher education institutions and libraries in Kerala are not equipped with assistive technologies, and most are not aware of the many ways these technologies can be applied. If proper assistive technologies and basic infrastructural facilities are added to existing library facilities in Kerala, most of the libraries can be transformed into an inclusive library for all or a learning resource centre. The administrators and management should need to realize that these people are not challenged by intelligence. Therefore, the outcome of the study would, it is hoped, provide valuable information to the academicians, librarians, sociologists, policy planners and the government.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed A, 2018. Perceptions of Using Assistive Technology for Students with Disabilities in the Classroom. *International Journal of Special Education*, Vol. 33, No. 1, pp. 129-139
- Ari IA and Fethi AI, 2010. Assistive technologies for students with disabilities: a survey of access and use in Turkish universities. *TOJET: The Turkish Online Journal of Educational Technology*, Vol. 9, No. 2, pp. 40-45. Retrieved from <http://search.proquest.com/openview/bac1a20cb696ff95c4d57e18129cd926/1?pq-origsite=gscholar>
- Bhattacharya I, Ramachandran A, Upadhyay N and Sharma M, 2013. Assistive Computing Technology for Enabling Differently-Abled Population in India: A User Driven Intervention. *International Journal of User-Driven Healthcare*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 33-43
- Census of India 2011. Retrieved from <http://censusindia.gov.in/>

- Chakravarty R and Mahajan P, 2013. Role of Libraries in Facilitating Reading Habits: Use of All Inclusive Assistive Technologies. *KIIT Journal of Library and Information Management*, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 28-33.
- Coleman M, 2011. Successful implementation of assistive technology to promote access to curriculum and instruction for students with physical disabilities. *Physical Disabilities: Education & Related Services*, Vol. 30, No. 2, pp. 2-22.
- Cummings EO, 2011. Assistive and adaptive technology resources. *Knowledge Quest*, Vol. 39, No. 3, pp. 70-73.
- Haque Md, Armanul Md, Nazmul Hasan A, Eamin Ali Md, Mahbubul Islam A, Farzana I and Md Mukul H, 2020. Physically Challenged Students at Rajshahi University in Bangladesh: a study on Information Need and Seeking Behavior with Special Focus on Library Use. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, Vol. 25, No. 6, pp. 14-24.
- Ilayaraja M and Manoharan A, 2012. An empirical study on library and information services to (pcs) physically-challenged students in the university library, Tiruchirappalli district. *TRANS Asian Journal of Marketing and Management Research*, Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 17-26.
- Lidström H and Hemmingsson H, 2014. Benefits of the use of ICT in school activities by students with motor, speech, visual, and hearing impairment: A literature review. *Scandinavian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, Vol. 21, No. 4, pp. 251-266. Retrieved from <http://www.researchgate.net/publication/260127804>
- Midhula Soman VS and Sudhier KG, 2018. Physically challenged student's use of library resources: A study in the state of Kerala. *National Conference on Role of Libraries in Creating a Knowledge Society (SALIS-2018)*. Alagappa University, Karaikudi.
- Sanaman G and Kumar S, 2015. User's perspectives towards assistive technologies available in NCR libraries of India. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, Vol. 35, No. 2, pp. 90-99.
- Solarin EOL, 2012. A survey of Library and Information services to physically-challenged students in Academic Libraries in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP/>
- Solarin EOL, 2013. Information and services provided to wheelchair mobile users in Nigeria: role of academic libraries. *International Journal of Academic Library and Information Science*, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 24-28.
- Tella YLA, Ademolake HBA and Adisa MY, 2015. Physically Challenged undergraduates: satisfaction with library and information services in Kwara state higher institutions. *Journal of Balkan Libraries Union*, Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 1-14. Retrieved from <http://www.balkanlibraries.org/journal>
- Venkatesha, Ramesh AN, Santhosh CR and Praveenkumar BL, 2016. Assistive technology for the physically challenged members of the library. In *National Conference on Library and Information Services for all: Reaching the Unreached in the Digital Era*. University of Mysore. (pp. 69-71). Retrieved from <http://eprints.uni-mysore.ac.in/id/eprint/18287>
- World report on disability. Retrieved from http://www.who.int/disabilities/world_report/2011/en/

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